

URBAN-WASTE – 690452 – D8.5

URBAN-WASTE

Urban strategies for Waste Management in Tourist Cities

D8.5 – Final Conference Report

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Abstract

This deliverable reports on the Final Conference which took place on 7 May 2019, as the final event marking the end of the project. Belonging to WP 8 on Communication and Dissemination, it was aimed at one last mass dissemination and communication activity targeting a wide audience composed of the most various stakeholders – EU institutions, tourism and waste associations, NGOs, local and regional authorities, industry, media and activists and individuals.

The deliverable will present the idea behind the Conference itself, the structure and the most valuable notes from the conference itself.

Contributors

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List of abbreviations

ACR+	Association of Cities and Regions for Recycling and Sustainable Resource management
CE	Consulta Europa
WP	Work Package
CoP	Communities of Practices
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
EU	The European Union
EC	European Commission
LCA	Local and Regional Authorities

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1. Preface

This Final Conference was organized a part of the communication and dissemination activities foreseen by the project. It came as one of the last such activities and served as an opportunity to present the key findings, outputs and achievements to a wide audience. And a what a wide audience it was, with 165 registered participants from different backgrounds – waste, tourism, NGOs, local and regional authorities, EU institutions, media, science with few curious individuals interested by the project's topic.

It has been three years since a consortium of 27 partners launched a Horizon 2020 project titled "URBAN-WASTE". The project brought together key stakeholders along the waste prevention and management, as well as the tourism value chain in order to develop eco-innovative and gender strategies in cities with high levels of tourism in order to reduce the urban waste production and improve municipal waste management.

11 pilot cities and regions, spanning across Europe – from Nicosia in the east to Ponta Delgada in the middle of the Atlantic Ocean and from Copenhagen in the north to Tenerife in the sub-tropical south, boarded this 3-years long journey redefining their tourism and waste management value chains, practices, approaches and principles in general. Thanks to a number of universities, NGOs and consultants who provided valuable input and skills, the pilots had the opportunity to assess their urban metabolism performances and look into improving certain processes in order to achieve more sustainable tourism locally.

Three specific objectives of the project that were common for all the 11 cities and regions and that brought together a large number of local stakeholders, experts, tourists, decision makers and more were developing integrated eco-innovative strategies for municipal waste policies, fostering and structuring a stakeholder inclusive framework for policy-making in waste management and addressing gender in waste prevention and management.

Three years later, these 11 cities and regions, together with their local stakeholders and the rest of the consortium were proud to be able to present the wider public, European institutions and organisations, local and regional authorities the outcomes, facts and findings and most importantly – the way forward that has been paved by the URBAN-WASTE project.

The Conference took place in Brussels, at Theatre Balsamine, in Schaerbeek, only few streets away from the European quarter, founded by Martine Wijckaert in 1974. Originally a part of a set of barracks surrounding Dailly square dating back to the 19th century which became abandoned at one point, the building was reclaimed and turned into an impressive setting which started hosting theatre plays, conferences and other events from 1981.

2. The objectives and the idea behind the Final Conference

Being a part of the communication and dissemination activities, the partner responsible for its organization was ACR+ who started developing the idea back in October 2018. The very first proposal of the structure and content took place in Lisbon, in November 2018, during the 3rd General Assembly of the project.

The main objective of the Final Conference was to summarise the work done over the last 3 years and highlight the most outstanding findings, results and achievements to the audience which would be composed of a set of various stakeholders representing the tourism and waste value chains, local, national and European policy makers. The Conference also had to give visibility to the 11 pilot cities and regions ("*pilots*" hereafter) and their stakeholders to share their experiences and present their achievements. Furthermore, the Final Conference had to serve as a place and opportunity to give public recognition to the signatories of the Charter of Commitments ("*the Charter*" hereafter), an initiative and campaign previously developed by the project as an outreach and mobilization activity.

Given the fact that the project consortium was composed of 27 project partners, including the 11 and taking into consideration the Conference's objectives, the very first task was to determine the structure of the Conference. This structure had to enable all the 11 pilots to present their achievements together with their local stakeholders, as well as give space for the acknowledgement and public recognition to the signatories of the Charter of Commitments, URBAN-WASTE's very own campaign which even turned into a movement at one point. Nonetheless, a large number of technical partners who contributed to the project with their skills, knowledge and scientific and technical work through researches, surveys, data analysis etc. were supposed to provide the audience with the background information on how certain eco-innovative measures were developed, as well as assessed at the later stage. During its lifetime, the project also created many synergies with other projects and external stakeholders whose participation was valuable for the dissemination of the URBAN-WASTE principles and approaches – many tourism related associations and industries, local and regional authorities outside the project's consortium and more.

The chosen date for the Final Conference was 7 May, based on the venue's availability, but even more than that, for the sake of convenience and having enough time after the Conference to close the finances, reporting and other follow up tasks. Based on the structure, agenda and choice of speakers which is described below, the Conference was titled "Waste management in Tourism. Does It Even Matter?".

2.1 Conference structure and proposed agenda

Being based in Brussels and having a long-standing experience in organizing such events, but also having seen many of them, ACR+'s idea to go for a storytelling experience was later proven to be the most adequate when it comes to keeping the audience's attention and also presenting the project's lifetime coherently and understandable for the audience. The very first draft of the agenda, presented in Lisbon during the 3rd General Assembly contained the following outline and the structure of the project:

Session 1: Key-note speeches

This session was imagined as the opening one, receiving the biggest attention from the audience which would also explain the very beginnings of the project – its objectives, relation to the Horizon 2020 programme, concept but also expected impacts. This session also had the intention to acknowledge those project partners who were behind the original idea and who carried out the project. Having been imagined as the most ceremonial part of the Conference, it was proposed to include the public recognition of those stakeholders who signed the Charter of Commitments.

Session 2: Key approaches, findings and deliverables

While the URBAN-WASTE project resulted in numerous interesting findings, being a kind of a groundbreaking project in terms its focus and field of activity, it was necessary to pick and highlight the most remarkable ones. However, the choice of speakers and findings had to make sense in terms of timeline but also to provide the necessary basis for the session foreseen for the afternoon. This was left to the Steering Committee to define and decide what is out there worth highlighting.

Session 3: Thematic debates; short presentations and panel discussions with guest facilitators

As mentioned already, one of the objectives of the Conference was to give space to the 11 pilots and their achievements. However, based on the experience from Mutual Learning events and Municipality Forums which preceded the Final Conference, where many pilots were reporting on their many measures and strategies, it was decided to look for a solution that would give each of the 11 pilots the opportunity to highlight their biggest achievements. Thematic debates were presented as panel discussion which would group the 11 pilots into clusters that would reflect the measure or strategy each of them developed and implemented that had the best results. The grouping was left to the project's Steering Committee to facilitate based on the results of the impact assessment that was about to commence in 2019. Furthermore, since one the objectives of the Conference was also to give visibility to the local stakeholders from the 11 pilots, such panel discussions were thought to be able to ensure their participation.

2.2 Side events

In order to enrich the Final Conference with other entertaining content, ACR+ started looking into potential activities which would be taking place during the breaks, as well as after the Conference itself in order to keep the audience busy. One of the reasons for this was also to keep them at the Conference long enough in order to have them attending as much of it as possible, knowing that the size of the audience in such events decreases with every break. The side events were also imagined as a place where the audience could expand their knowledge, experience and acquired information from the sessions. Since these events were secondary to the main programme, having less importance attributed to them, the idea was to explore the interest of those who register through the registration form. The responses would eventually confirm or reject the need and interest in these events. The proposed events included:

- Photo exhibition – as mentioned before, the organisers thought that giving all the 11 pilots and their stakeholder the time to present all their activities could backfire in form of less interesting and monotone presentations with the audience left alone to make conclusions on the most remarkable achievements; therefore, the idea was to expand and enrich the 3rd session and the thematic debates with a visual presentation of the measures and strategies the pilots deployed highlighting the achievement and their impacts, whether environmental, social or economic

- Manual workshops – ateliers that would be focusing on “DIY” activities or repair principles, creating useful (travel) accessories from secondary material attended by the audience during the breaks
- WasteApp and Food Waste Tracker demonstrations – these two ICT tools were developed within the project's framework and it was foreseen to have their presentation during the Final Conference; however, being more visual and operational than a video/photo presentation it was proposed to their developers to ensure a demonstration would take place during the Conference
- Film screening – the organisers wanted enrich the Conference with a less formal part of it and propose the audience a film screening that would match the topic; what was left was to explore the logistical possibilities and find an appropriate film

3. Logistics and the build-up of the Final Conference

The first several months of 2019 were dedicated to finding logistical solutions and putting the previously presented idea into action. While ACR+ was drafting the final agenda with the rest of the project's steering committee, it also took care of the logistics in Brussels.

3.1 Venue

The guiding objective of the organisers in Brussels was to have a venue that could be considered as unconventional to the usual conference setting in Brussels. ACR+ wanted to offer the project partners and the audience something different, something unusual and an informal venue that would make them feel more comfortable and that would make the Conference itself more enjoyable. In terms of locations, the venue had to be close to the transport hubs (airport, train stations) and well served by public transportation and at the same time, close to the so-called European quarter for convenience and accessibility reasons. ACR+ decided to disregard any typical conference venues and look for a place that could offer alternative solutions to typical conference settings.

Few venues were contacted, including Les Halles de Schaerbeek and Maison des Arts, before the final choice was made – theatre Balsamine in Schaerbeek.

The Balsamine theatre was founded by Martine Wijckaert in 1974. At the beginning it was a simple legal entity, a non-profit organisation, making it possible to obtain subsidies for artistic creation. The theatre back then didn't imply any building and thus neither a venue nor a form of residency for artists. It nevertheless obtained subsidies on an ad hoc basis, enabling Martine Wijckaert's first shows to be produced. These productions were born from a mode of urban nomadism: abandoned sites became sets on which the shows were performed. In 1981, the Balsamine theatre moved temporarily to the abandoned former Dailly barracks.

These barracks had been abandoned for several years and they were discovered in their original state. The site had all the virtues of a fictive city and this quality invited the theatre to establish itself there.

Theatre, visual art and music mixed and brought together on the site numerous artists discovering there a work and experimentation residency. At the same time as managing the Balsamine, established in the barracks, Martine Wijckaert pursued her own artistic work there. Activities and renovation works were focused on one of

the barracks' particular sites, baptized the "amphitheatre", because of its architectural characteristics - it was in fact a former military auditorium, structured in a semicircle.

The current theatre, with its contemporary style yet retaining the singularity of the original theatre, dates back to 2001 and represents the work of architect Francis Metzger, for which he took 3rd prize in architecture at the Costa Rica Biennale. The exterior and the interior of the theatre are presented in the following Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1. The exterior of the Balsamine theatre

Figure 2. The interior of the Balsamine theatre (the bar, the amphitheatre and the terrace)

With its 170 seats and a large stage that allows the scenography to be adjusted to different sessions maximising their impact and theatre lights highlighting the important features of each session, the Balsamine theatre turned out to be a great choice for the Conference venue.

3.2 Catering

Three different caterers were contacted once the venue was chosen, all local, some of them even from the imminent neighbourhood in order to minimise even more the environmental footprint of the catering service. After contacting Boentje Café, the first zero waste café in Brussels, known for its practices and principles, Kamilou catering service, which is known for its cooperation with local producers of seasonal and organic ingredients and Shake & Eat, a conceptual catering service that combines zero waste, seasonality, organic production and low-impact principles in its businesses, the offer from Shake & Eat was chosen as the most suitable for the needs of the Conference.

ACR+ had also thought of eventual food wastage and therefore partnered up with Belgium Kitchen, a platform that distributes food waste to those in need.

3.3 Speakers and the final agenda

Based on the presented structure and the different sessions the agenda would include this task had the objective to appoint suitable speakers for the different topics planned. It was decided not to focus too much on visual presentations, as they often distract the speakers from talking to the audience, but also alienates the audience from the speaker. Since the format of the Conference was suggested to be storytelling, the stage imagined to represent a “talk-show studio” resembling the Conference host’s living room in the first plan with a screen put in the second plan, which would be used only occasionally to announce the different sessions and speakers and eventually show few slideshows. The Conference’s host title and the tasks which go with it were allocated to Erneszt Kovacs, of ACR+.

Key-note speeches

The key-note speeches were allocated to the project coordinator, the author, the donor, the host of the Conference, as well as the Charter of Commitments. Due to the unavailability of the speaker on behalf of the European Commission, her intervention was moved to the next session, which opened up more space for the Charter.

The organisers also wanted to have someone from the local or regional authority to be present not only to welcome the participants, but also to shortly reflect on the local reality, whether from the tourism or waste management perspective. For this role, ACR+ managed to get on board Fadila Laanan, the minister responsible for waste management, science and innovation at the Brussels Capital Region. Michelle Perello of Consulta Europa, as the project’s author was asked to present the project’s objectives and the idea behind it, while Silvia Bertran of the Government of the Canary Islands was asked to intervene on the behalf of the project coordinator. On behalf of the hosts, ACR+, their Secretary General, Françoise Bonnet was asked to give a speech on the importance of cooperation and networking between local and regional authorities and to host the ceremony on Charter of Commitments. Speaking of the Charter, it is worth mentioning the very high attention the Charter had drawn over the last months prior to the Conference what led to the transformation of this part of the Conference (a simple presentation of the Charter with its signatories) into a proper signing ceremony with 8 new signatories joining the Charter. This was identified as a great contribution to the Conference as it would increase the outreach and make it more ceremonial and interesting for the media. The 8 new signatories who were invited to Brussels were the

Municipality of Krakow, the city of Brugge, the Tourism Agency of Corsica, the waste management company AMIU from Genoa, as well as the 4 Fisheries Local Action Groups representing the entire island of Sardinia.

Key approaches, findings and deliverables

As this session was supposed to present the key outputs and observations the technical and scientific partners made over the last three years, of which there were many, together with the Steering Committee it was decided to present the following outputs:

- Urban metabolism principles describing the impact of tourism on waste arisings and waste management in general in order to allow the audience to understand the underlying principles and correlation between these two processes; to be presented by Gudrun Obersteiner of BOKU
- Situational analysis of consumption and waste behaviours and patterns in tourism which further explained some occurrences in tourism and how tourists perceive waste management when on holidays, as well as the role of this analysis in defining future eco-innovative measures for the 11 pilots; to be presented by Erik Louw of TU Delft
- Observations and achievements from the gender mainstreaming perspective which was identified as an important part of this session, as the project had a strong gender-based research; to be presented by Susan Buckingham, the project's gender auditor
- How the cooperation between authorities and local stakeholders was set up and what were the outcomes of this cooperation; to be presented by Javier Lopez of Consulta Europa

This session also featured the intervention of Marie Yeroyanni of the European Commission which was originally planned for the first session with other key-note speeches.

This order of speakers and topics was also chosen in order to reflect the timeline of the project and enable the audience to understand the links between the tasks and results.

Thematic debates; short presentations and panel discussions with guest facilitators

The solution for a rather delicate task to enable all the 11 pilots to present their achievements and efforts, as well as include their local stakeholders and furthermore to ensure participation of external stakeholders and targeted associations, institutions etc. was to cluster the 11 pilots into 4 thematic debates, each facilitated by an external and neutral facilitator. This solution was thought to be able to ensure a focused and well-defined sessions, allowing the pilots to focus on what they did the best with the participation of some of their stakeholders and, at the same time, open the possibility for interventions from external stakeholders, too. When it comes to the audience, this format would allow them to understand the variety of URBAN-WASTE measures and strategies and potential areas of improvement. It was decided to run these debates without slideshows and visual presentations in order to have the audience focusing on the panelists and their stories.

The four thematic debates that made it to the final agenda were:

- ICT solution in waste management for a more sustainable tourism: this debate was imagined to have the focus on two valuable outputs of the project – the WasteApp and the Food Waste tracker with the participation of not only the tools' developers, but also the pilots who had good results in their implementation, as well as local stakeholders who were the final-end users. This debate was supposed to have as panelists University of Las Palmas in Gran Canaria, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Municipality of Santander, Cabildo de Tenerife and Hotel Tigaiga of Puerto de la Cruz as the local

stakeholder. Milosz Momot of the European Commission's Tourism, Emerging and Creative Industries, DG GROW.

- Waste at seas: as there were several pilots who decided to focus on marine litter and waste that is generated on ships it was decided to dedicate one debate to this topic. This debate had the objective to explore the cooperation between local and regional authorities and local stakeholders in the field of maritime tourism and marine ecosystems and present some potential measures and partnerships between them. The Dubrovnik – Neretva County, the municipality of Kavala, the municipality of Copenhagen with their local stakeholder the Copenhagen – Malmo port and the European Cruise Lines International Association were invited to the panel with the European Sea ports Organisation to facilitate it.
- Food waste in tourism – tools for its prevention: a large number of pilots were basing their measures and strategies on this issue and therefore this panel would have even 4 pilots planned to have their stories heard. The municipalities of Nicosia, Florence, Syracuse and the Nice Cote d'Azur Metropole were invited to join this panel, as well as WTB Hotels, Florence's local stakeholder. European Commission's DG Environment was asked to facilitate it.
- Hospitality sector's contribution to sustainable tourism: as the Municipalities of Lisbon and Ponta Delgada were the most ambitious and successful in reaching out to local hospitality establishments, the last debate would put their approach in the spotlight. The municipality of Lisbon suggested Hotel 3K Europa to have their side of the story shared. HOTREC, the European Association of HORECA establishments was also invited as an external contributor, as well as NECSTouR to facilitate the panel.

3.4 Side events

The previously presented ideas for side events were very much welcomed by the project consortium. Once the organisers saw the venue's potentials, they started making the ideas more concrete. All the side events and the ideas behind that are described below, as well as the Conference itself were followed by a cocktail reception, to mark a hopefully successful Conference and the end of the project.

Photo Exhibition

The photo exhibition was decided to be an accompanying part of the pilots' stories and their achievements. The most important reason for organising this exhibition was to complete the pilots' stories with a visual presentation of them, due to the fact that slideshows were decided not to be a part of the debates. Eleven A1 photos were designed and printed and were planned to be displayed at the theatre's hallway. Two of them are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Examples of the photos that would be displayed as a part of the exhibition

Manual workshops

Several local ateliers and workshop organisers were contacted to provide manual workshops during the Conference's breaks, including creative upcycling, re-use and repair activities which could result in some recycled and DIY travel accessories. RecyK, Fais-le toi meme, la Mouvance Recup' were only some of them. In the end, Kmille and DaddyCookiz, two artists from Liege, Belgium who proposed creative solutions were also available were invited to organise their ateliers. Kmille was supposed to be on upcycling and making travel accessories out of secondary material and DaddyCookiz, more musical – making music on recuperated material such as random tools, equipment but also wonky vegetables and other material. This atelier also proposed an evening animation during the cocktail reception using the sounds recorded during the day.

WasteApp and Food Waste Tracker demonstrations

The two partners who developed these two ICT tools, the University of Las Palmas in Gran Canaria and the Swedish Agricultural University were asked to provide these two demonstrations, which would also take place during the breaks. While the WasteApp would consider the Conference as a city for itself in order to be able to recreate and demonstrate the App's features, the Food Waste Tracker would use the food waste and biowaste coming from the musical atelier.

Film Screening

After a short desk research and reading reviews on recent releases which would match the topic of the Conference, the organisers decided to get in touch with the creators of HONDAR 2050 which was released in 2018. It is a 45 minutes documentary which was thought to fit perfectly with the programme of the day and offer the audience a rather laid back and informal opportunity to relax after the Conference itself. The film is rich in beautiful pictures and aerial images of the Basque region in Spain where the film was shot and where the main protagonist Carlos Arrola lives and surfs.

Directed by Cesare Maglioni, HONDAR 2050 is a triple action project. The first action is the creation of a documentary about the marine waste problem on the coast of Euskadi, by Cesare Maglioni. Thanks to this documentary we see what people don't want to see, through the eyes of the artist Carlos and his search for answers. Secondly, along the narrated story, Carlos creates a number of art works with the wastes found in the sea or on the coast. It costs us to become aware of the problem but through these criticising works, our

environmental print becomes visible. These works will be displayed in an exposition in the Cristina Enea Foundation in Donostia. The last action is based on a forum debate and citizen exchange of ideas about the marine waste problem.

It was also the pleasure to be able to invite Carlos Arrola himself who was available for a discussion that was planned for after the screening.

4. The day of the Conference

165 people registered for the Conference, including 42 participants coming from different project partners, 35 speakers (from project partners and externals) and 88 external participants. These 88 participants represented a variety of backgrounds as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The structure and backgrounds of external participants.

Waste management	Tourism	NGO	LCAs	EU	Media	Science	Other	Individuals
11	5	15	17	5	7	1	19	8

Among these 165 registered participants we had 75 male and 90 female participants.

It was interesting to see how these external participants heard about the Conference, in order to assess the best communication methods. 34 of them were directly invited, 21 found out about the Conference through their internal communication channels within their organisations and 14 through external communication channels (networking), 17 through the URBAN-WASTE dedicated communication channels (newsletter, Facebook, Twitter) and 2 through search engines.

Another important feedback the organisers got from the registration forms was the interest in staying for the film screening. Since the numbers showed 62 interested and 62 “maybes” it was a good indicator and proof for organizing the screening. One more indicator that could already confirm some expectations the organisers had was the interest of registered participants in the 3 different sessions. All the 3 of them received nearly equal interest from those who registered: 60 external participants interested in session 1, 61 in session 2 and 58 in session 3. This confirmed that the proposed structure, speakers and format sounded interesting to the most of participants.

However, even though the number of registered participants was quite impressive, only 110 people actually attended the Conference. The reason for this could lie in the fact that the spring of 2019 was full of bank holidays, quite close to each other in Belgium, but also elsewhere in Europe. One of these holidays, only for the EU institutions employees though - the Europe Day, was the same week, so the organisers assumed from the very beginning that as the Conference approaches certain participants would actually become unavailable to attend the Conference. The most obvious reason for not having anyone from the European Parliament, for instance, apart from the holiday, was also the fact that the Conference took place only two weeks prior to the elections for the European Parliament.

4.1 Notes from the Final Conference

09.00 – 09.15 | Opening of the Final Conference and a welcome note from the Brussels Capital region; *Fadila Laanan, Minister, Brussels Capital Region*

Fadila Laanan was invited to the Conference as a representative of the Conference's "host region". She reflected on some occurrences in Brussels and what the tourism looks like. Apart from the tourism itself, she highlighted the high impact of commuters who are coming to Brussels from the surrounding provinces and leaving the same day, on a daily basis. This creates certain pressures in certain parts of the city, especially bus and train stations and a pressure on the waste collection infrastructure. She also shared some details on waste management in Brussels and explained to the audience the capacities and competences different regional agencies have when it comes to waste management. She closed her speech with welcoming the audience to Brussels and wishing them all a successful conference.

Erneszt Kovacs, ACR+ as the Conference host and Fadila Laanan opening the Conference

09.15 – 09.25 | Introduction to the project, background and objectives; *Michelle Perello, Consulta Europa*

Michelle Perello, who stands behind the project proposal and who can be considered as its main author of this project, shared with the audience the ideas and inspiration she had for this project nearly 4 years ago. Beside mentioning these, she also reflected on the objectives of the proposal and how did they fit those of the European Union and Horizon 2020 programme in particular. Michelle Perello also looked back at how the consortium was built and how to make sure the necessary tasks would be carried out.

09.25 – 09.40 | Why did 11 European cities and regions decide to tackle waste management in tourism?; Silvia Bertran, Communication Advisor, Government of the Canary Islands

On behalf of the project coordinator – the Government of the Canary Islands, Silvia Bertran explained the audience the reason why her Government decided to step up and take the lead in this rather groundbreaking project. Coming from the Canary Islands, she already saw examples of the issue the URBAN-WASTE project was dealing with. This is why her Government, but also the 11 pilot cities and regions decided to act, as they are all on the frontline of this problem.

09.40 – 10.05 | Roles, opportunities and responsibilities of cities and regions in the transition towards circular economy; Françoise Bonnet, Secretary General, ACR+

Francoise Bonnet, being the Secretary General of a 25 years old association of cities and regions highlighted few important facts when it comes to the roles, opportunities and responsibilities of cities and regions. She said “Cities and regions are very often the ones who are on the frontline of implementing and contextualizing different strategies and policies. They are the ones who have to put those strategies into a framework and practice that reflect the reality and very often this reality differs from one region to another” and added “Cities and regions in Europe are full of good practices, some of them considered even best practices, replicable solutions and ideas. These practices, solutions and ideas must go beyond the limits and borders of where they were created.”

Furthermore, a part of her intervention was also the signing ceremony of the Charter of Commitments. According to the feedback the ceremony was very pleasant and inspiring. Even 8 new signatories came to Brussels that day, joining the club of other 19 signatories who previously joined it. Françoise Bonnet invited on stage some of those who signed it already to welcome the new ones. Mr Pedro Furtado of the Municipality of Ponta Delgada, Ms Susanne Lindeneg of the Municipality of Copenhagen, Mr Louka Papayianni of the Municipality of Nicosia were present in Brussels and they welcomed Ms Tiziana Merlino of AMIU Genova, Italy, Mr Waclaw Skubida of the Municipality of Krakow, Poland, Ms Nanette Mapertuis of the Collectivity of Corsica, France, Ms Mercedes Van Volcem of the city of Brugge, Belgium, as well as the four Fisheries Local Action Groups of Sardinia, covering the entire island and representing 19 different municipalities who delegated their signatures to Ms Nicolette Piras, Ms Marta Cadinu, Mr Davide Cao, Mr Alessandro Murana.

Françoise Bonnet of ACR+ during the signing ceremony of the Charter of Commitments

10.35 – 10.55 | Waste management in tourism: why does it even matter?, Gudrun Obersteiner, BOKU University

Gudrun Obersteiner and her BOKU Waste management Institute from Vienna who led the work on urban metabolism and defining the baseline scenario in the 11 pilots explained the methodologies that were used, the way data was collected and most importantly the observations made based on that data. She interpreted them and summarized to the audience what impact tourism has on waste management depending on different spatial and socio-economic characteristics of the 11 pilots. The second part of her presentation was focusing more on the final stage of the project and the impact

assessment which was done by comparing the baseline scenarios with the monitoring results coming from the pilots.

10.55 – 11.10 | Situational analysis of consumption and waste behaviours and patterns in tourism; Erik Louw, TU Delft

Erik Louw and TU Delft were one of the partners which were responsible for another important part of the project – assessing the consumption and waste behaviours of tourist and how tourists perceive waste management when on holidays. This was indeed an interesting presentation and it drew attention of the audience, as the results were coming from a survey that was conducted in the 112 pilots with more than 600 respondents. Among these respondents there were also people working in tourism industry as well as in waste management, what completed the picture and later helped the pilots to develop measures which would make the real impact, based on the hotspots identified.

11.10 – 11.30 | It takes two to tango: why and how addressing gender is important for waste management; Susan Buckingham, gender auditor

The gender auditor's role was to monitor the project's development and intervene with gender mainstreaming principles. Susan Buckingham presented not only her work, duties and tasks but also some rather interesting findings on the different involvement, capacities and representation of men and women in the two fields – tourism and waste management. She also expanded Erik Louw's presentation on behavior with the perception of tourism activities and waste management from the men and women's perspectives, too. She

closed her presentation with conclusions but also highlighted certain cities that progressed significantly in terms of gender equality.

11.30 – 11.45 | Sustainable tourism as a joint venture: cooperation between authorities and local stakeholders; Javier Lopez, Consulta Europa

Following the previous presentations on the initial assessments and baseline scenarios, as well as observed occurrences in waste arising and tourism activities, Javier Lopez presented the Communities of Practices model that the URBAN-WASTE project used to bring together the local and regional authorities around the same table and initiate the discussion which would eventually lead to defining various eco-innovative measures applicable locally. He highlighted few important principles which were proven to affect the process, as well as few learning points.

11.45 – 12.00 | Innovating Cities Policy R&I Agenda; Marie Yeroyanni, European Commission, DG Research and Innovation

A valuable presentation came from Marie Yeroyanni of the European Commission which came with the overview of EU's priorities and objectives for the upcoming years, as well as presenting different programmes and support mechanisms for cities to benefit from in fulfilling these objectives and targets. Her intervention was important because she also reflected on the URBAN-WASTE project and how did its objectives match those of the EU and why did URBAN-WASTE got selected as one of the beneficiaries of the Horizon 2020 programme, in the first place.

The morning ended with a questions and answers session allowing the audience to further discuss these findings and observations with the four speakers of the Session 2.

The long lunch break served as a good opportunity for the participants to spend a bit more time in the workshops organized in the hallway, making wallets, notebooks etc. and explore the exhibition and the ICT tools demonstrations.

Photos of the manual workshops

The afternoon had a completely different format, as the presentations were replaced by thematic debates around 4 topics which had been picked up by the most of the pilots to be dealt with.

14.00 – 14.40 | IT solutions in waste management for a more sustainable tourism; facilitated by Milosz Momot, deputy Head of Tourism, Emerging and Creative Industries Unit at DG GROW

- Celia Gilsanz Gomez, Municipality of Santander
- Alejandro Molowny, Cabildo de Tenerife
- Mattias Eriksson, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
- Rafael Perez Jimenez, University of Las Palmas in Gran Canaria
- Enrique Talg, Hotel Tigaiga, Puerto de la Cruz

This panel had the objective to explain the audience the development of the two IT tools, developed by ULPGC and Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, as well as their deployment in Santander and Tenerife. After Rafael Perez Jimenez and Mattias Eriksson explain the functionalities and benefits of these tools, Celia Gilsanz Gomez and Alejandro Molowny on behalf of their pilots shared their experiences in the deployment but also good and bad aspects of their use. The joint conclusion was that the implementation times was rather short for being able to make concrete conclusions, but both tools could see improvements and future developments in order to become even more applicable in reality. Alejandro Molowny also reported on the acceptance factor of those who the food waste tracker is intended for (hotels, restaurants) and challenges he was facing – whether spatial, whether in form of trust, but also skills necessary to use it etc. Enrique Talg was there to share his first hand experiences coming from his hotel in Tenerife.

Panel discussion on IT tools

14.45 – 15.25 | Waste at seas; facilitated by Sotiris Raptis, Senior Policy Advisor for Environment and Safety, European Sea Ports Organisation

- Susanne Lindeneg, City of Copenhagen
- Iva Pozniak, Dubrovnik – Neretva county
- Fotios Tsagkas, DIAAMATH – East Macedonia and Thrace Waste Management Company
- Annette Berg Neergaard, Copenhagen Malmö Port
- Martyn Griffiths (replacing Tom Broadley), Cruise Lines International Association Europe

The panel discussion on waste at seas brought together an interesting mix of panelists including LCAs, but also industry associations and of course, local stakeholders. While Susan Lindegen and Annette Berg Neergaard were telling their story on measures deployed at the Copenhagen – Malmo port, Fotios Tsagkas shared the experiences coming from Kavala on the same topic and their cooperation with the local port. Iva Pozniak, however, diversified the discussion, as the Dubrovnik – Neretva County focus their efforts on marine litter and cooperation with a whole range of local stakeholders including NGOs, fishermen associations and others. Her focus also triggered an interesting discussion with the audience and participants coming from the fisheries associations on the role of local fishermen in combatting marine litter. The panel was also interesting for another fact – the two external participants, one facilitator and one panelist representing the Cruiser Lines International Association. Sotiris Raptis, who is a senior policy officer at the European Sea Ports Organisation shared some knowledge on the recent policy changes but also upcoming ones and his own concerns in what direction should ports, cruisers and other marine vessels industries go in the future in terms of policies.

Panel discussion on waste at seas

16.00 – 16.40 | Food waste in tourism – tools for its prevention; facilitated by: Jean-Benoit Bel, senior project manager, ACR+ (replying Ben Caspar, policy officer, Environmental Knowledge, Eco-Innovation and SMEs, DG ENV)

- Yoann Billon, Metropole Nice – Côte d’Azur
- Maria Thiseos, Municipality of Nicosia
- Barbara Sarnari, Ambiente Italia on behalf of Municipality of Syracuse
- Lorella Lentucci, Tuscany region
- Claudio Delli, WTB Hotels

The panel discussion facilitated by Jean-Benoit Bel offered a very interesting insight in a diverse set of potential measures LCAs could implement locally in order to fight food waste. While Yoann Billon shared his experience on working with restaurants and introducing doggy bags to both restaurant managers and their guests, Lorella Lentucci talked about the food waste that doesn’t get taken home by the guests. Together with her local stakeholder, Claudio Delli, she explained what kind of partnerships they had to create in order to divert leftover food to those communities and social groups in need. Maria Thiseos reported on Nicosia’s programme of food waste advisors which were acting as peers locally and working on the sensibilization of the local hotels and

restaurants. Barbara Sarnari, on behalf of the municipality of Syracuse wrapped up the panel with Syracuses new scheme – the collection of cooking oil.

Panel discussion on food waste

16:45 – 17:25 | Hospitality sector's contribution to sustainable tourism; facilitated by: Olle Jonang, Vastra Gotaland and NECSTour Executive Committee member

- Rute Carvalho, Municipality of Lisbon
- Gisela Maria Costa Nascimento, Fundo Regional Para a Ciência e Tecnologia
- Ana Cristina Chaves, Hotel 3K Lisbon
- Christian de Barrin, HOTREC, European Association of HORECA establishments

The last panel discussion was similar yet different to the previous one on food waste as it was focusing more on the HORECA establishments (hospitality, restaurants and cafes). Both Lisbon and Ponta Delgada identifies local hotels and restaurants to work with on specific measures that would imply their efforts in changing certain practices, such as separate collection in the hotel rooms, but also introducing certain waste prevention measures, such as replacing single use products with refillable and reusable ones. Ana Chaves was there on behalf of a local stakeholder from Lisbon to explain what such involvement meant for them and what were the indirect benefits. Christian de Barrin completed the discussion with the perspective of the European HORECA Association and what are the good practices already out there in Europe.

Panel discussion on HORECA establishments

17:30 – 17:45 | Closing remarks; Lorenzo Bono, Ambiente Italia

The closing remarks were reserved for Lorenzo Bono of Ambiente Italia, someone who has spent quite some time with the 11 pilots on all the phases the pilots went through – the implementation, monitoring and reporting. He shared the most remarkable observations and conclusions and also looked at the potentials for the way forward.

Left for the very end of the Conference, almost as an Annex, not being a part of the official agenda, the HONDAR 2050m documentary announced earlier still attracted quite a lot of attention and sacrifice from the Conference participants as they stayed for even more after a full day of information, debates and presentations. The screening also saw some new faces as there were several external guests who came to see the film. In the end it turned out to be rewarding as the film featured not only impressive pictures and scenery of the coast but also the concern and engagement of the local community. Thanks to the presence of Carlos Arrola, the film's main actor and protagonist, the audience could join the very lively discussion which followed the film between the host Erneszt Kovacs and Carlos himself.

The evening was closed with a cocktail reception for the participants.

Final Conference group photo

All the photos from the Final Conference can be seen [here](#) and the presentations [here](#).

Annex I: Final Conference Agenda

URBAN-WASTE Final Conference Waste management in Tourism. Why does it matter?

Theatre Balsamine, Brussels; 07 May 2019

SESSION 1: Keynote speeches

08.30 – 09.00	Registrations
09.00 – 09.15	Introduction to the project and its background; <i>Michelle Perello, Consulta Europa</i>
09.15 – 09.25	Opening of the Final Conference and a welcome note from the Brussels Capital region; <i>Fadila Laanan, Minister, Brussels Capital Region</i>
09.25 – 09.40	Why did 11 European cities and regions decide to tackle waste management in tourism?; <i>Silvia Bertran, Communication Advisor, Government of the Canary Islands</i>
09.40 – 10.05	Roles, opportunities and responsibilities of cities and regions in the transition towards circular economy – signing ceremony of the Charter of Commitments; <i>Françoise Bonnet, Secretary General, ACR+</i>

*Coffee break

SESSION 2: Key approaches, findings and deliverables

10.35 – 10.55	Tourism and waste: why does it even matter?; <i>Gudrun Obersteiner, BOKU</i>
10.55 – 11.10	Situational analysis of consumption and waste behaviours and patterns in tourism; <i>Erik Louw, TU Delft</i>
11.10 – 11.30	It takes two to tango: why and how addressing gender is important for waste management; <i>Susan Buckingham, gender auditor</i>
11.30 – 11.45	Sustainable tourism as a joint venture: cooperation between authorities and stakeholders; <i>Javier Lopez, Consulta Europa</i>
11.45 – 12.00	Innovating Cities Policy R&I Agenda; <i>Marie Yeroyanni, European Commission, DG Research and Innovation</i>
12.00 – 12.15	Questions and answers

SESSION 3: Thematic debates *panel discussions with guest facilitators*

14.00 – 14.40	<p>IT solutions in waste management for a more sustainable tourism <i>facilitated by Milosz Momot, deputy Head of Unit, Tourism, Emerging and Creative Industries, DG GROW</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Celia Gilsanz Gomez, <i>Municipality of Santander</i> - Alejandro Molowny, <i>Cabildo de Tenerife</i> - Mattias Eriksson, <i>Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences</i> - Rafael Perez Jimenez, <i>University of Las Palmas in Gran Canaria</i> - Enrique Talg, <i>Hotel Tigaiga, Puerto de la Cruz, Tenerife</i>
14.45 – 15.25	<p>Waste at seas <i>facilitated by Sotiris Raptis, Senior Policy Advisor for Environment and Safety, European Sea Ports Organisation</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Susanne Lindeneg, <i>City of Copenhagen</i> - Annette Berg Neergaard, <i>Copenhagen Malmö Port</i> - Iva Pozniak, <i>Dubrovnik – Neretva County</i> - Fotios Tsagkas, <i>DIAAMATH – East Macedonia and Thrace Waste Management Company</i> - Tom Boardley, <i>Cruise Lines International Association Europe</i> <p style="text-align: center;">* Coffee break</p>
16.00 – 16.40	<p>Food waste <i>facilitated by Ben Caspar, policy officer, Environmental Knowledge, Eco-Innovation and SMEs, DG ENV</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Barbara Sarnari, <i>Municipality of Syracuse (Ambiente Italia)</i> - Yoann Billon, <i>Metropole Nice Cote d'Azur</i> - Maria Thiseos, <i>Municipality of Nicosia</i> - Lorella Lentucci, <i>Tuscany region</i> - Claudio Delli, <i>WTB Hotels, Florence</i>
16.45 – 17.25	<p>Hospitality sector <i>facilitated by Olle Jonang, NECSTouR Executive Committee member and co-leader of NECSTouR working group on Smart Destinations</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rute Carvalho, <i>Municipality of Lisbon</i> - Gisela Maria Costa Nascimento, <i>Fundo Regional Para a Ciência e Tecnologia</i> - Ana Cristina Chaves, <i>Hotel 3K Lisbon</i> - Christian de Barrin, <i>HOTREC, European Association of HORECA establishments</i>
17.30 – 17.45	<p>Closing remarks, <i>Lorenzo Bono, Ambiente Italia</i></p>

* The coffee breaks and lunch will be served in the hallway outside the amphitheatre; we kindly ask you not to bring drinks and food back into the amphitheatre

Workshops and ateliers throughout the day

A set of workshops and ateliers will be taking place during the Conference's coffee and lunch breaks. The participants are more than welcome to visit some of the stands and the accompanying exhibition set up in order to celebrate the 11 URBAN-WASTE pilot cities and regions and their efforts made during the project's lifetime. Some of the workshops include:

Knille: upcycling ideas for travel accessories

Knille is a young designer and DIY enthusiast who tries to give different material a second life – usually different from what those materials were originally made for. Her work is inspired by the overconsumption patterns these days. This is how aluminium cans turn into jewellery, old t-shirts into stylish necklaces and for the occasion of the URBAN-WASTE Final Conference, she will be making few travel accessories, too: travel diaries out of old cardboard, paper and other material and wallets out of packaging material. See her other creations here.

DaddyCookiz: musical journey of wasted objects

Daddy Cookiz is a multimedia artist from Liege, already a proven reggae band member and a solo artist, as well. But his musical portfolio and repertoire don't end with large festivals and blasting sound systems. Nearly whatever he touches starts making music and so does waste and much more. As a social worker, he knows to spend days with kids, youngsters and other social groups providing various workshops. For the Conference, he is coming with keys that have nothing to open anymore and screw keys, vegetables and his DIY music equipment. The result – we will let you discover it at the end of the Conference. You can see here what he does.

WasteApp: a gamification mobile app to make your holidays a bit more exciting

The URBAN-WASTE's very own mobile app, currently deployed in the 11 pilot cities and regions was developed within the project's framework. It can enhance your holidays and visits to the 11 pilots by adding a gamification feature to it. Be environmentally responsible and win awards. A simple demonstration stand will be set up during the Conference for you to see what it is exactly about! Until then, read more about it here.

Food waste tracker: a handy helper in your kitchen for optimising your portions

Another app developed by the project partners and tested in numerous restaurants and hotels – while it will also have its 5 minutes of glory during the panel discussions, it will also have a dedicated spot at the Conference, during the breaks where the participants can see what it can do.

Evening programme

18.30 – 19.30 | HONDAR 2050 screening and discussion with the film's main protagonist Carlos Arrola

HONDAR 2050 is a triple action project. The first action is the creation of a documentary about the marine waste problem on the coast of Euskadi, by Cesare Maglioni. Thanks to this documentary we see what people don't want to see, through the eyes of the artist Carlos Arrola and his search for answers. Secondly, along the narrated story, Carlos creates a number of art works with the wastes found in the sea or on the coast. It costs us to become aware of the problem but through these criticising works, our environmental print becomes visible. These works will be displayed in an exposition in the Cristina Enea Foundation in Donostia. The last action is based on a forum debate and citizen exchange of ideas about the marine waste problem. This encounter took place the day of the documentary's premier in the AQUARIUM of Donostia.

19.45 | Cocktail reception and musical animation

Media Partner:

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